

Research Article

Heavy metal ions in milk samples collected from animals feed with city effluent irrigated fodder

***Sajid Farid and Musa Kaleem Baloch**

Department of Chemistry, Gomal University, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan.

*Corresponding author's E-mail: sajidnfciefr@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Untreated city effluent is used as source of irrigation in Faisalabad, Pakistan for raising different crops including fodder which is used for feeding the animals in the cattle's farms. This paper reports a study to assess the risks and opportunities associated with this practice by determining heavy metals concentration in milk, which is used in daily life excessively. Heavy metals and other properties were measured in typical effluents, four soils and three fodder crops. It was found that the city effluent increased heavy metals concentrations in the soil and ultimately in fodder. Furthermore Heavy metals concentrations in the milk were found above those normally associated with suitability for human consumption. It is recommended that effluent should be treated before it's used for raising different crops.

Key words: City effluents. Irrigation quality, heavy metals, soil, fodder, milk

Introduction:

Milk is the characteristic secretion of the mammary glands of all the mammals, which meets the nutritional needs of the body better than any other single food. It contains the food constituents including protein, carbohydrates, fat, minerals and vitamins. Furthermore contains these dietary essentials in fairly suitable proportions (Atherton, 1982). Quantity and quality of the milk depends on better health condition of the animals. The mineral requirements of the animals must be adequately met for better health. The inorganic mineral elements necessary for nutrition include Ca, P, Fe, Cu, Mn, Mg, Na, K, Cl, I, Co and Zn (Atherton, 1982; Castle and Watkins, 1984). Although many minerals are termed as essential to the animals when feed correctly, the same mineral can be toxic and even lethal when fed in excess. Thus the supplementation of a ration with minerals particularly trace elements, should be done with great care. The concentration of trace elements in diet affects milk quality because the nutrients are removed from the blood by mammary glands, converted in to milk and secreted into the udder. Milk is secreted into the udder more or less throughout the day. Nutrients for milk production must from the feed, either directly or indirectly via body reserves of nutrients, which come originally from the animal's feed (Cullison, 1975). Trace elements produced by various environmental pollution sources might reach animal's milk through forage, so the growing environmental pollution has increased worries about milk quality.

Due to arid and semi arid condition of the Pakistan in most of the parts of the country receive rain fall around 20cm (Nazir, 1994), which is not sufficient for the growing any crop of economical importance. In order to overcome this situation, it is so common to utilize city effluent for raising different crops including fodder around the big cities. Mostly this city effluent is contaminated with untreated industrial effluents (Ghafoor et al, 1994). Usually a few industries are usually equipped with satisfactory operating treatment plants (Nabi et al., 2001). This City effluent at the same time is a good source of irrigation, nutrients and organic matter (Ahmad et al, 1994). It has been observed that in selected areas farmers not utilize even a single grain of fertilizer for economical production of fodder. City effluent at the same time is also a big source of heavy metals like Cadmium, Chromium, Nickel and Zinc (Khan, et al 1994). Due to more multidimensional and versatile industries in the Faisalabad, the extent of heavy metals like Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Lead (Pb) and Nickel (Ni) contamination was evaluated in the city effluent, soils fodder and milk. The objective of study were

1. To evaluate the metal ions concentration in the city effluents.
2. To determine the concentration of metal ions in soils under city effluents irrigation.
3. To determine the degree of metal ion contamination in the effluent-irrigated crops.
4. To evaluate the toxic level of metals ions in the milk of animal grazed by effluents irrigated grass.

Materials and methods:**Experimental site:**

To determine the metal ions contamination in the effluent irrigated soils twelve farmer's fields were selected where untreated city effluent had been used as source of irrigation for more than twenty five years. The sole criterion for the selection of the sampling sites was that there are many cattle farms. The animals of these farms are feed on fodder grown by using untreated city effluent as source of irrigation.

Analysis of city effluent:

City effluent sampling was carried out from the open channel flowing through the farmer's field located in Gandakhue, Mulkhanwala, Awanwala and Khanuwala at Faisalabad. Eight samples on weekly basis were collected from each selected site after rinsing the plastic jars thrice with the effluent. These samples were analysed for pH, EC (Electrical Conductivity), RSC (Residual Sodium Carbonate) and SAR (Sodium Adsorption Ratio) by following the standard methods described by US Salinity Laboratory Staff, 1954. Heavy metals like Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Lead (Pb) and Nickel (Ni) concentration were determined on Varian AA-1445 series Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AOAC, 1984).

Sampling and analysis of soils:

Soil sampling was performed at different depths (0-15, 15-30, 30-60 and 60-90 cm) of four selected locations of effluent irrigated field with the help of soil sampler (auger). The samples were air dried, ground with the wooden articles, mixed thoroughly and passed through 2mm sieve and stored in labeled plastic bags. These were later analysed for pHs, E_{ce} (Electrical conductivity of the soil extract) and SAR by following the standard methods given by the US Salinity Laboratory Staff (1954)

Heavy metals like Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Lead (Pb) and Nickel (Ni) concentration in soil samples was determined by digesting the sample in the acid mixture (HNO₃- H₂O-HCl). Heavy metals concentration was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer Model Varian Spectra AA250 plus (Rowell, 1994).

Fodder crop sampling and analysis:

Fodder crop samples were collected from each field randomly. The fodder crops considered for the purpose were maize (*Zea mays* L.), Berseem (*Trifolium alexandrinum* L.) and sorghum [(*Sorghum bicolor* L.) Moench]. Samples were washed with 1% HCl, followed by three to four washing with distilled water to remove the foreign material then spread on a clean paper for drying. These samples were then oven dried at 60-70 °C. The dried samples were digested in di-acid mixture of Nitric acid (HNO₃) and Perchloric acid (HClO₄). Heavy metals like Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr) Lead (Pb) and Nickel (Ni) concentration in the prepared samples was determined by using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Model Varian Spectra AA250 plus (AOAC, 1984).

Milk sampling and analysis:

Milk samples were collected from the cattle farms located in the areas under study. Samples were collected immediately after milking from cows and buffalos. The samples were taken 8 times in a month. 10ml milk sample was used for analysis. The dish was transferred to the furnace and heated to white ash at 450 °C for 12 hours. After mineralization the material was dissolved in 10 HCl solution. Than further dilution was made with 1% HCl solution and Heavy metals like Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Lead (Pb) and Nickel (Ni) concentration in the prepared samples was determined by using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer Model Varian Spectra AA250 plus.

Results and discussions:**Irrigation quality of untreated city effluents:**

Mean values of chemical composition of the city effluents collected from all four sites are given in Table-1. The considerable variation with respect to location was observed which was probably due to different nature of wastewater produced by industries working at different sites. Higher mean values of the EC (3.09 dSm⁻¹), RSC (4.83 mmolcL⁻¹), SAR (15.41 (mmolcL⁻¹)^{1/2}), Cd (0.03 mgL⁻¹), Cr(0.64 mgL⁻¹) and Ni (0.23 mgL⁻¹) than the permissible

levels suggested by U.S. Salinity Lab. Staff (1954) and Ayres and Westcot, (1985) may leads to the development of salination/ Sodication as well accumulation of heavy metals in the soils receiving this effluent as source of irrigation.

Table1: Chemical composition of untreated city effluent samples collected from different locations in Faisalabad, Pakistan

Parameters	Units	Range	Mean	Standard Deviation	Permissible Limit
pH	-	7.15 – 7.95	7.48	0.19	-
EC	dSm ⁻¹	2.10 – 4.26	3.09	0.49	1.50
RSC	mmol _c L ⁻¹	1.90 – 7.93	4.84	1.08	2.00
SAR	(mmol _c L ⁻¹) ^{1/2}	10.78 – 20.85	15.41	2.47	10.00
Cd	mg L ⁻¹	0.01 – 0.05	0.03	0.01	0.01
Cr	mg L ⁻¹	0.07 – 2.16	0.64	0.41	0.10
Pb	mg L ⁻¹	0.08 – 0.34	0.16	0.05	5.00
Ni	mg L ⁻¹	0.02 – 0.41	0.23	0.08	0.20

Characteristics of the city effluent irrigated soils:

Analysis of soil samples collected from different locations, indicted that the soils are alkaline in reaction (pH >7.00), non-saline (EC < 4.00dSm⁻¹) and Non-sodic (SAR15.00mmol_cL⁻¹)

Table 2 The pHs, ECe and SAR of soil samples receiving city effluent

Soil under fodder	Soil depth (cm)				
	0 - 15	15-30	30-60	60-90	90-120
pHs					
Maize	7.70(0.12)	7.80(0.09)	7.86(0.05)	7.97(0.13)	8.20(0.07)
Lucerne	7.72(0.11)	7.83(0.07)	7.85(0.19)	7.95(0.11)	8.13(0.11)
Berseem	7.76(0.11)	7.79(0.11)	7.89(0.07)	7.96(0.12)	8.18(0.14)
ECe (dS/m)					
Maize	3.69(0.69)	3.44(0.65)	2.83(0.62)	2.41(0.28)	1.77(0.59)
Lucerne	3.36(0.75)	3.24(0.10)	2.68(0.49)	2.12(0.57)	1.80(0.53)
Berseem	3.49(0.96)	3.31(0.87)	2.84(0.50)	2.59(0.61)	2.21(0.32)
SAR (mmol _c L ⁻¹) ^{1/2}					
Maize	13.52(3.36)	12.81(3.56)	12.35(2.78)	10.42(2.26)	9.77(1.28)
Lucerne	13.03(2.84)	12.49(2.76)	11.47(2.31)	10.63(1.52)	9.78(1.15)
Berseem	13.58(2.97)	13.05(2.65)	12.16(2.45)	10.91(1.59)	10.03(0.85)

Heavy Metals Concentration in Soil:

Cadmium (Cd²⁺):

Total cadmium in soils under study ranged from 1.34 to 3.68 mg/Kg (Table 3) while the permissible limit is 0.50 mg/Kg (Rowell, 1994). Generally, total cadmium in soil is more than 0.50 mg /Kg and considered an evidence of soil contamination. Our results in the upper 30 cm (i.e., ranged from 3.03 to 3.68) layer indicated the cadmium concentration well above the maximum allowable limit of 3.00, 3.00 and 2.00 mg/Kg used in Poland, Great Brittan and Germany, respectively, and were lower than the maximum allowable limits of 5.00 and 8.00 mg/Kg used in Austria and Canada, respectively (Rattan, 2002). The possible sources of Cd²⁺ in sewage water and soils is contributed from a number of sources, like industry (metallurgy, etc), proximity to highways and sewage sludge application (McBride, 1994) and Faisalabad sewage is no exception to these sources.

Chromium (Cr³⁺)

Results were listed in the Table 3 and indicated that Cr³⁺ concentration in the soil samples were in the range of 119.42 - 155.58 mg/Kg. Higher values in the upper and lower values in the deeper layers indicated the low mobility of

the Cr^{3+} in the soil. Chromium concentration was quite higher than the maximum allowable limits, 100, 75, 100, 50 ppm used by Austria, Canada, Poland and Great Britain, respectively (Rattan, 2002).

Lead (Pb^{2+})

Total Pb^{2+} in soils ranged from 6.32 in deeper layer to 25.83 mg/Kg in the upper layer (Table 3). In all the cases, total Pb^{2+} was below the permissible limit of 50 mg/Kg (Rowell, 1994). Although, it was much higher in the soil surface (30 cm) as compared to lower depths. The high Pb^{2+} accumulation in the surface layer might be due to the continuous irrigation of soils with metal contaminated city effluent and also due to less mobility of Pb^{2+} within the soils, particularly under the alkaline soil conditions (McBride, 1994). In addition, industrial smoke, Auto vehicle exhaust and fly ashes also be contributed towards addition of Pb^{2+} in the surface layers of soils which condensed near/ onto the soils surface. Consistently, the soils at most of sites contained much higher total and bio-available forms of Pb^{2+} because the sites are located quite close to a metalloid road on which automobiles are playing round the clock producing smoke by burning the leaded mineral soils.

Nickel (Ni^{2+})

Total Ni^{2+} contents in soil ranged from 13.80 to 32.25 mg/kg (Table 3) in 0-30 cm soil depth. About 4% soils contained total Ni^{2+} , less than the permissible limit of 25 mg/kg (Rowell, 1994). This may be due to low solubility of Ni^{2+} at ambient alkaline pH. Its mobility is rated as medium in acid soils and becomes very low in neutral to alkaline soils (McBride, 1994).

Table 3 Heavy metal ions concentrations (mg/Kg) of soil samples receiving city effluent

Soil under crop	Soil depth (cm)				
	0 – 15	15-30	30-60	60-90	90-120
Cadmium					
Maize	3.59(0.35)	3.39(0.25)	2.19(0.33)	1.86(0.47)	1.54(0.49)
Lucerne	3.64(0.17)	3.26(0.17)	2.03(0.24)	1.74(0.43)	1.34(0.30)
Berseem	3.61(0.27)	3.21(0.35)	2.11(0.52)	1.74(0.46)	1.49(0.43)
Chromium					
Maize	143.00(21.31)	129.08(18.07)	127.67(14.09)	124.50(15.69)	126.58(13.13)
Lucerne	151.50(26.86)	137.58(12.41)	132.83(13.62)	135.75(9.65)	129.92(10.14)
Berseem	144.83(21.42)	149.83(17.41)	132.58(10.23)	143.00(15.96)	126.00(7.94)
Lead					
Maize	25.83(3.58)	20.25(0.96)	12.72(1.77)	8.66(0.67)	7.54(0.96)
Lucerne	24.01(1.52)	21.00(1.50)	15.08(1.68)	9.44(1.00)	7.08(0.65)
Berseem	24.52(1.74)	20.93(1.45)	16.86(2.00)	8.25(1.70)	6.45(0.94)
Nickel					
Maize	24.46(2.95)	23.53(0.73)	21.52(0.86)	16.40(1.55)	13.80(0.82)
Lucerne	27.12(0.92)	23.52(0.90)	20.16(0.97)	17.17(1.64)	14.65(1.93)
Berseem	27.32(0.91)	23.37(0.97)	20.49(1.24)	18.42(1.08)	15.25(0.78)

Metal ions in fodder crops irrigated by city effluent

Fodder crops irrigated by city effluents were analysed and the results are captioned below:

Cadmium (Cd^{2+})

The average values of cadmium found in polluted areas was 4 folds higher as compared to unpolluted areas (Table 4). The maximum tolerable level of Cd^{2+} in cattle's diet is 0.5 mg Kg^{-1} , whereas the excessive level of Cd^{2+} can cause

cattle poisoning. Symptoms of Cd^{2+} poisoning in cattle include poor appetite, slower growth, anemia, retarded testicular development, enlarge joints, scaly skin, liver and kidney damage and increase mortality (Gillespie, 1987). The observed values are quite higher and could be potentially dangerous to animals' health as corroborated by poor appetite and slower growth in some of the animals of the study area.

Chromium (Cr^{3+})

The average concentration of Cr^{3+} observed in Maize, Lucerne and Berseem were 29.34, 27.33 and 31.08 for polluted and 1.34, 1.43 and 1.23 for unpolluted areas, respectively (Table 4). Although a wide margin of safety exists between the amount of Cr^{3+} ordinarily consumed and those likely to be harmful to the body but still there is no recommended level of Cr^{3+} in animals' diet.

Lead (Pb^{2+})

The average values of Pb^{2+} were found more than 12 times in case of polluted areas as compared to unpolluted areas. Excessive levels can cause Pb^{2+} poisoning. Symptoms of Pb^{2+} poisoning in cattle includes dullness, loss of appetite, abdominal pain with constipation, sometimes followed by diarrhoea and after two or three days bellowing, staggering, snapping of eyelids, muscular twitching, frothing at the mouth and convulsive seizures. The maximum tolerable level of Pb^{2+} in cattle's diet is 30 mg Kg^{-1} (Gillespie, 1987) and the observed level lower was less than this limit (Table 4).

Nickel (Ni^{2+})

The average concentration of Ni^{2+} observed in Maize, Lucerne and Berseem were 20.78, 21.83 and 21.19, respectively in polluted areas and 4.63, 2.75, and 2.40, respectively in unpolluted areas (Table 4). The maximum tolerable level of Ni^{2+} in cattle's diet is 50 mg Kg^{-1} as reported by Gillespie (1987). Church, 1971 reported that the permissible limit is less than 100 mg Kg^{-1} . As such the observed values are quite lower than the permissible levels.

Heavy metal ions in milk

Milk is the characteristic secretion of the mammary glands of all the mammals (Roadhouse and Henderson, 1950, Khattak, 2004, Atherton, 1982), which meets the nutritional needs of the body better than any other single food. It contains the food constituents, including protein, carbohydrates, fat, minerals and vitamins. Furthermore, it contains these dietary essentials in fairly suitable proportions (Atherton, 1982).

Quantity and quality of the milk depends on better health condition of the animals. The mineral requirements of the animals must be adequately met for better health. The inorganic mineral elements necessary for nutrition include Ca, P, Fe, Cu, Mn, Mg, Na, K, Cl, I, Co and Zn (Atherton, 1982; Castle and Watkins, 1984). Although many minerals are termed as essential to the animals when feed correctly, the same mineral can be toxic and even lethal when fed in excess. Thus the supplementation of a ration with minerals particularly trace elements, should be performed with great care. The concentration of trace elements in diet affects milk quality because the nutrients are removed from the blood by mammary glands, converted in to milk and secreted into the udder. Milk is secreted into the udder, more or less throughout the day. For nutrients milk production, animals must be fed, either directly or indirectly via body reserves of nutrients, which come originally from the animals feed. Trace elements produced by various environmental pollution sources might reach animal's milk through forage. Therefore, the growing environmental pollution has increased worries about milk quality (Cullison, 1975; Sabir et al 2003; Oskarsson et al, 1995). Analysis results of the milk samples are captioned in the coming section and tabulated in Table 25.

Cadmium (Cd^{2+})

Cadmium is a highly toxic and has been implicated in some cases of poisoning through food. Minute quantities of cadmium are suspected to be responsible for adverse changes in arteries of human kidneys (APHA, 1995). Threefold (0.06 mg/L) higher concentration of Cd^{2+} in the urban areas were detected than Un-urban areas (0.02 mg/L) in the milk of cow and Buffalo. The detected values were quite lower than the cadmium concentration detected by Khattak et al, (2004) and Koen et al (1982) but comparable with the one detected by Lokeshwari and Chandrappa (2006). It has been further studied that the cadmium concentration is quite lower than the permissible level of 0.10 ppm (Lokeshwari and Chandrappa, 2006).

Table 4 Heavy metal ions concentration (mg/Kg) in fodder samples collected from polluted and unpolluted areas.

Heavy metals	Fodder	Polluted Area			Unpolluted Area		
		Range	Mean	S.D	Range	Mean	S.D
Cadmium	Maize	0.54 – 0.94	0.75	0.14	0.12 – 0.20	0.16	0.03
	Lucern	0.80 – 1.07	0.94	0.09	0.16 – 0.22	0.19	0.03
	Berseen	0.78 – 1.04	0.93	0.08	0.16 – 0.24	0.20	0.04
Chromium	Maize	20.18 – 38.12	29.34	5.32	1.20 – 1.50	1.34	0.14
	Lucern	20.18 – 35.48	27.33	5.03	1.34 – 1.61	1.43	0.17
	Berseen	27.26 – 40.16	31.08	3.81	1.20 – 1.34	1.23	0.09
Lead	Maize	22.89 – 27.36	24.28	1.44	1.89 – 2.34	2.09	0.19
	Lucern	21.56 – 26.38	23.61	1.71	1.67– 2.15	1.92	0.21
	Berseen	18.37 – 27.64	25.06	2.51	1.39– 2.00	1.70	0.28
Nickel	Maize	16.38 – 25.34	20.78	2.64	3.50 – 6.70	4.63	1.46
	Lucern	17.94 – 25.36	21.83	2.20	2.30 – 3.60	2.75	0.59
	Berseen	18.37 – 24.52	21.19	1.90	2.10 – 2.80	2.40	0.29

Chromium (Cr³⁺)

In the animal milk collected from polluted areas had about 0.29 ppm concentration as compared to the (0.10ppm) one obtained for unpolluted area (Table 5). In a similar study elevated level of chromium was also observed in the milk samples collected from the areas where city effluents used for raising forage (Khattak et al, 2004).

Lead (Pb²⁺)

Lead concentration in the milk samples collected from polluted areas was fivefold (0.11 ppm) higher as compared to unpolluted area (0.02 pmm). Similarly higher level of lead has been reported by Dwivedi and Swarup (1995) in their studies on milk collected from urban areas of India. Reported values were well below the permissible values quoted by Hough et al (2003) and Loeshwari and Chandrappa (2006) of 0.02 ppm in milk. Environmental factor played a vital role in the elevated level of forage which ultimately effects the Pb concentration in the milk. (Khattak et al, 2004; Tripathi et al, 1999; Ayyadurai et al 1998).

Nickel (Ni²⁺)

Milk samples collected from the polluted areas had about threefold (0.11 ppm) higher concentration of nickel as compared to unpolluted area (0.04) which reflects the nickel pollution (Table 5) in the environment of the study area. Underwood (1977) reported lower values in the milk collected from unpolluted areas than the detected values of Ni in this study. Furthermore it had been investigated that the detected values were lower than the upper limits reported by Walstra and Robert (1984) and Khattak et al (2004).

Table 5 Heavy metal ions concentration (ppm) in milk samples collected from polluted and unpolluted areas.

Heavy metals	Polluted Areas			Un-Polluted Areas		
	Range	Mean	S.D	Range	Mean	S.D
Cadmium	0.03-0.08	0.06	0.02	0.01-0.04	0.02	0.01
Chromium	0.18-0.36	0.29	0.06	0.07-0.20	0.10	0.04
Lead	0.06-0.16	0.11	0.03	0.03-0.00	0.02	0.01
Nickel	0.08-0.16	0.11	0.02	0.02-0.07	0.04	0.02

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